

IMPREGNATION PROSESS IN OPEN MOLDING METHOD USING MULTI-FILAMENT WINDING

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ABSTRACT

Since the molding time of thermoplastic resin composite is shorter than that of thermosetting resin composites, high cycle molding is possible. Also the multi-filament winding (MFW) method has been developed as new fabrication method to produce composite pipes. The MFW method which winds many reinforcing fibers simultaneously on a core material (mandrel) can produce composite pipes with high productivity. The produce of a thermoplastic composite by MFW method can improve the productivity furthermore. By adopting the open molding, male and female molds and large-scale equipment are not required. By combining the MFW method and the open molding method, the reduction of not only the productivity but also the production cost for CFRTP pipe can be expected. However, the thermoplastic resin has a problem that its viscosity is so high that impregnation is difficult as compared with a thermosetting resin.

In this study, the goal is to develop an open molding method using MFW, with a fibrous intermediate material in which a thermoplastic resin is partially impregnated into carbon fiber bundles. The heater position and heating temperature were changed for making an optimum heating condition clear. CFRTP pipes were fabricated at several heater positions and heater temperatures. And the impregnation states of the CFRTP pipes were compared and evaluated by cross-sectional observation.

From these results, it was cleared that the heating conditions are important for obtaining a CFRTP pipes in an excellent impregnated state that the fiber bundle is in the temperature range of 215°C to 300°C in front of the winding point. Furthermore, impregnation process was also clarified at the heating condition.

1 INTRODUCTION

The thermoplastic resin composite material with carbon fiber is excellent in recyclability and has a low impact on the natural environment. Since the thermoplastic resin melts by reheating, it is also excellent in secondary process ability. Furthermore, since the molding time of thermoplastic resin composite materials is shorter than that of thermosetting resin, high cycle molding is possible. Most of these thermoplastic resin composite materials are produced by closed molding method. For the closed molding methods a pair of male and female molds are used. And the costs of the molds and large-scale equipment raise the production cost. By comparison, in open molding methods, since either of the male and female molds is used, it is possible to reduce the cost of the mold.

In addition, the multi-filament winding (MFW) method has been developed as new fabrication method. The MFW method which winds multiple reinforcing fibers simultaneously on a core material (mandrel) can produce composite pipes with high productivity [1]. By combining the MFW method and the open molding method, the problem of production cost can be solved. However, the thermoplastic resin has a problem that its viscosity is so high that impregnation is difficult as compared with a thermosetting resin. In the past, research on thermoplastic resin composites (CFRTP) using the MFW method has not been conducted. Therefore, in order to establish a molding method, it is necessary to clarify molding conditions. A research has been reported on the molding conditions of an open molding method using braiding for making CFRTP pipes [2]. In this report, an intermediate

material composed of carbon fiber and PA6 is used. We thought that this method could be applied to MFW.

In this study, the goal is to develop an open molding method using MFW, with a fibrous intermediate material in which a thermoplastic resin is partially impregnated into carbon fiber bundles. The heating conditions were changed and the optimum conditions was clarified. And the impregnation states of the CFRTP pipes were compared and evaluated by cross-sectional observation.

2 MFW METHOD AND OPEN MOLDING METHOD

Fig.1 shows a schematic drawing of the MFW machine and the structure. A circular base plate is installed at the center of the machine, and on the plate, nozzle guides are attached radially toward the center of the machine. The mandrel is set vertically to the base plate, and reciprocates longitudinally and rotates. The carbon fibers are supplied from bobbins on which the fibers are stored, and go through the nozzle guides onto the mandrel. As the mandrel rotates and reciprocates, the carbon fibers are wound on the mandrel. The position where the carbon fiber is wound on the mandrel is called the winding point. The rotational speed and reciprocating speed of the mandrel control fiber orientation angle to satisfy the required mechanical characteristics of the CFRP pipe.

A feature of the MFW structure is that a large number of continuous fibers are used to cover the entire mandrel with the same angle. Because the next layer is further formed on top of it, there is no crossing of the fibers with changes in the position of the fibers above and below. It makes a non-crimp structure where there is no fiber undulation (crimp). Therefore, superior mechanical properties can be expected to other reinforcing structure with crimp structure such as braiding and weaving.

A heater was attached to the MFW machine to perform open molding process of the CFRTP pipe using this machine. The schematic drawing of a heater near the winding point is shown in Fig.2. In this method, the thermoforming can be performed simultaneously during the winding process. When the fiber bundle is wound on the mandrel through the heater, it is heated and resin is melted. After it goes through the heater, the melted resin is naturally cooled and solidified.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of MFW machine and structure.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of heater position.

3 TEST METHOD

3.1 Winding and molding conditions

In this experiment, the winding conditions were fixed as four-layer lamination so that the orientation angle was $\pm 45^\circ$. A short wavelength infrared omega heater (manufactured by Heureus) was used. The infrared energy output by the heater was controlled by voltage using the control unit. The parameters of the heating conditions in "the position of the heater" and "infrared energy by the controller" were changed, and the optimum molding conditions of the thermoplastic MFW method were investigated.

As a fiber bundle, an intermediate material in which nylon (LEXTER 8500, manufactured by Mitsubishi Gas Chemical Company, Inc.: melting point 215°C .) was partially impregnated into a carbon fiber bundle (TR50S-12k, manufactured by Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) was used.

In the case of the open molding for braiding, a heater was installed in front of braiding point, the yarn was placed on the mandrel after heating, and heating improved the impregnation property [2]. Therefore, the conditions for installing the heater were a position closer to the nozzle side (17mm from the winding point (heater position A)) and a position placed at the winding point (heater position B). Pipe molding was carried out by setting the outputs of the heaters at 120V, 140V, 160V and 180V at the heater positions A and B, respectively. The names of the specimens at the heater position A were A-120, A-140, A-160, and A-180. Similarly, the specimens at the heater position B were B-120, B-140, B-160, and B-180.

3.2 Evaluating methods

3.2.1 Impregnation stats

The cross section of the specimens was observed, and the un-impregnation ratio and the void ratio were measured to quantify the state of impregnation. A schematic drawing of the measurement of the un-impregnation area and the void area is shown in Fig.3. The un-impregnation ratio and the void ratio were calculated using the following equation after extracting a range of $1/4$ of the pipe cross section.

$$\text{Un-impregnation ratio} = \text{Un-impregnation area} / \text{Fiber bundle area} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Void ratio} = \text{Void area} / \text{Observation area} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Schematic drawing of the un-impregnation area and the void area.

3.2.2 Temperature distribution

The temperature distributions of the fiber bundles near the winding point during molding were measured using an infrared thermographic camera (manufactured by Testo SE&Co. KGaA.). The temperature distribution of the fiber bundle was graphed, with the temperature distribution until the fiber bundle supplied from the nozzle guide reached the winding point as temperature on the vertical axis and the distance on winding point on the horizontal axis.

4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Impregnation states

In A-140, A-160, B-160, and B-180, the resin on the surface of the specimens was deteriorated and turned to brown. In A-180, there was a gap between the fiber bundles. Fig.4 show photographs of the appearance of the specimens with and without gaps between the fiber bundles, and the specimens which the resin on the surface was turned to brown in the appearance observation of the specimens produced under each condition.

In addition, the cross-sectional photograph of the specimens A is shown in Fig.5, and B is shown in Fig.6. Fig.7 shows the relationship between the un-impregnation ratio and the voltage and Fig.8 shows the relationship between void ratio and the voltage, measured by cross-sectional observation. The un-impregnation ratio of the heater position A were 22.3%, 15.6%, 39.2% and 36.2%, sequentially from 120V. On the other hand, the un-impregnation ratio of the heater position B were 1.8%, 2.4%, 1.3% and 1.7%. The void ratio of heater position A were 8.9%, 6.3%, 17.5%, 20.9%, and the void ratio of heater position B is 0.4%, 1.8%, 0.3%, 1.2%, etc. In comparison, it showed a low value.

Figure 4: Photograph of specimens with and without gaps between the fiber bundles, and specimens which the resin on the surface was turned brown.

Figure 5: Cross-sectional photograph of the specimens of A

Figure 6: Cross-sectional photograph of the specimens of B

Figure 7: Relationship between the un-impregnation ratio and the voltage.

Figure 8: Relationship between the void ratio and the voltage.

4.2 Temperature distribution

The temperature of the three fiber bundles in front of the winding point was measured. The temperature distribution of the fiber bundle was measured from the nozzle guide to the winding point. The relationship between the temperature of the fiber bundle and the distance to the winding point at each voltage at the heater position A is shown in Fig.9. Similarly, the heater position B is shown in Fig.10. (The red line is the melting point).The maximum temperature of the fiber bundle was about 300°C, 350°C, 380°C, and 400°C, sequentially from 120V of the heater position A. The heater position B was about 270°C, 290°C, 330°C and 330°C. Since the melting point of the resin used this time is 215°C, it was confirmed that the melting point was exceeded at 120V of the heater position B. It was confirmed that the resin began to deteriorate at a maximum temperature of about 330°C. because it had been discoloured by B-160.

Figure 9: Relationship between the distance from nozzle guide to winding point and fiber bundle temperature at heater position A.

Figure 10: Relationship between the distance from nozzle guide to winding point and fiber bundle temperature at heater position B.

4.3 Discussion

The optimum heating condition, heated location and heated temperature on fiber bundles, was clarified from these test results to obtain a CFRTP pipe with good impregnation. The heated location was controlled by heater position. Heater position B was better suited for the impregnation than heater position A. From the temperature distribution results, the maximum temperatures in the both cases of heater position A and B exceed the melting point. At the winding point, the temperature on the fiber bundle in the case of heater position A decreased to the melting point or lower of it. In the case of the heater position B, the temperature was kept higher temperature than melting point at the winding point. Accordingly, the heater position B indicated the much lower un-impregnation ratio and the void ratio than the heater position A.

The infrared energy emitted from the heater, which determines the heating temperature range, was controlled by the voltage value of the heater controller. Un-impregnation ratio and void ratio of all cases at heater position B were much lower than those at heater position A. However, when the resin was heated so much that it had thermal deterioration or burnout of the resin. According to the result of B-160, discoloration of the surface resin to brown occurred at the maximum temperature of 330°C. In the case of the maximum temperature of 400°C of A-180, a gap was observed between carbon fiber bundles due to the burning out of the resin. At B-140, the maximum temperature was 300 °C, and the resin had not thermal deterioration and burnout, and a pipe in an excellent impregnated state was obtained. In other words, it was found that the heating temperature range suitable for molding is the melting point temperature 215°C to 300°C. The optimum molding conditions were clarified as follows,

- the heated location was 10 mm front side of the winding point to the winding point
- the heating temperature was from 215°C to 300°C.

At the above optimum heating conditions, the impregnation process of this forming method is explained below. The resin was heated to the temperature above the melting point, liquefied before the winding point, and impregnated into the fiber bundle. At the winding point, the fiber bundle was wound on the mandrel in the molten state of resin with deforming cross sectional shape of fiber bundle. The deformation causes resin flow. And some of un-impregnation portions move to the outside of fiber bundle. Therefore the impregnation state was improved.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we developed the thermoplastic MFW method as an open molding method. The parameters of "heater position" and "output of heater by controller" were changed, and optimum molding conditions of the thermoplastic MFW method were examined. From this result, the heating conditions are important for obtaining a CFRTP pipes in an excellent impregnated state that the fiber bundle is in the temperature range of 215°C to 300°C, 10mm in front of the winding point. In addition, it was found that the installation position of the heater was important to realize the heating conditions, and the best for heating at the winding point.

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